

ENZYMES IN SNAKE VENOM. PART V. DETECTION OF DIPEPTIDASE, POLYPEPTIDASE, CARBOXY-POLYPEPTIDASE AND ESTERASE IN DIFFERENT SNAKE VENOMS.

BY B. N. GHOSH, P. K. DUTT AND D. K. CHOWDHURY.

In this paper the results so far obtained regarding the presence of cholin-esterase, and various peptidases in the venoms of a number of snakes, have been recorded.

In a series of papers (Ghosh *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 450, 627 ; 1937, **14**, 564 ; 1938, **15**, 471) it has been shown by us that the proteolytic enzyme present in snake venom resembles trypsin in all the properties investigated so far and hence suggestion has been made that the proteinase is identical with trypsin. A number of other enzymes in snake venom has also been detected recently. Roy (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1938, **26**, 241) has found that the venom of cobra (*Naja naja*) contains an esterase which hydrolyses ethyl butyrate. Iyengar and co-workers (*Current Sci.*, 1938, **7**, 53) and also Ghosh and co-workers have found that cobra venom contains an enzyme which can hydrolyse acetylcholine. In addition to these, we have detected the presence of such enzymes as polypeptidase, dipeptidase and carboxypolypeptidase in the venoms of snakes belonging both to the *Colubridae* and the *Viperidae* groups. The results so far obtained regarding the presence of polypeptidase, dipeptidase, carboxypolypeptidase and choline-esterase in different venoms are recorded in this paper.

Dipeptidase.

The properties of purified dipeptidase, prepared from yeast and gut of animals, have been studied by Grassman and Dyckerhoff (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1928, **179**, 41) and Waldschmidt-Leitz, Balls and Waldschmidt-Grasser (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1926, **156**, 68). They have found that this enzyme can hydrolyse dipeptides like glycylglycine which contains no asymmetric carbon atom and hence optically inactive and glycyl-*l*-leucine which is optically active, but it cannot hydrolyse dipeptides like glycyl-*d*-leucine, which does not occur in nature. In the course of our investigation on the enzymes in snake venoms, we have found a dipeptidase in the venoms of cobra (*Naja*

naja), banded krait (*B. Fasciatus*), *Echis carinata* and *Vipera russellii*. Like the gut or yeast dipeptidase, this peptidase in venom can hydrolyse glycylglycine and *l*-leucylglycine, but not the *dextro*-rotatory forms of the dipeptides like *d*-leucylglycine. This will be evident from the data recorded in Table I. The course of hydrolysis was followed by Sørensen's method of formol titration. The experimental procedure was exactly the same as described by Ghosh and co-workers (*loc. cit.*). The concentration of the substrates used was 0.008M and the concentration of the venoms-used was 0.1 % in each case. The p_H of the substrate-venom solution was 7.0.

TABLE I.

0.01N-NaOH required (in c.c.) for titration of 5 c.c. of the solution after 24 hours' incubation at 36°.

Cobra venom.			
Substrate.	Control.	Venom+substrate.	Diff.
<i>l</i> -Leucyl- <i>l</i> -tyrosine	... 1.52 c.c.	2.42 c.c.	0.90 c.c.
<i>l</i> -Leucylglycine	... 1.30	1.74	0.44
<i>d</i> -Leucylglycine	... 1.30	1.30	0.00
Glycylglycine	... 8.80	9.45	0.65
Russell's viper.			
<i>l</i> -Leucyl- <i>l</i> -tyrosine	... 1.55 c.c.	2.65 c.c.	1.10 c.c.
<i>l</i> -Leucylglycine	... 1.25	1.60	0.35
<i>d</i> -Leucylglycine	... 1.25	1.25	0.00
Glycylglycine	... 8.80	9.55	0.75
B. Fasciatus.			
<i>l</i> -Leucyl- <i>l</i> -tyrosine	... 1.55 c.c.	2.11 c.c.	0.56 c.c.
<i>l</i> -Leucylglycine	... 1.20	1.85	0.65
<i>d</i> -Leucylglycine	... 1.25	1.25	0.00
Glycylglycine	... 8.70	9.40	0.70

TABLE I (contd.).

Echis carinata.				
L-Leucyl-L-tyrosine	...	1'60 c.c.	4'80 c.c.	3'20 c.c.
L-Leucylglycine	...	1'40	2'55	1'15
d-Leucylglycine	...	1'40	1'40	0'00
Glycylglycine	...	8'75	9'55	0'80

Polypeptidase.

The properties of purified polypeptidase obtained from yeast and gut of animals have been investigated by Grassman and Dyckerhoff (*loc. cit.*) and Waldschmidt-Leitz and Balls (*Ber.*, 1930, 68, 1203). It has been found that this enzyme attacks the naturally occurring *laevo*-rotatory forms of the polypeptides only and not the *dextro*-rotatory forms. We have found the presence of this enzyme in the venoms of *Naja naja*, *Vipera russellii*, *Echis carinata* and *B. Fasciatus*. The results are recorded in Table II. The concentration of the solutions with respect to the substrates was 0'008M and with respect to the venoms was 0'1 % in all the cases recorded below. It will be noticed from the data in Table II that the enzyme can hydrolyse *l*-leucylglycylglycine and not *d*-leucylglycylglycine. This seems to indicate that the polypeptide molecule is attacked by the enzyme on the end containing the free amino group.

TABLE II.

0'01N-NaOH solution required (in c.c.) for titration of 5 c.c. of the solution after 24 hours' incubation at 36°.

Cobra venom.				
Substrate.	Control.	Venom + substrate.		Diff.
L-Leucylglycylglycine	...	1'40 c.c.	5'40 c.c.	4'00 c.c.
d-Leucylglycylglycine	...	1'40	1'40	0'00
Russell's viper.				
L-Leucylglycylglycine	...	1'35 c.c.	2'36 c.c.	1'01 c.c.
d-Leucylglycylglycine	...	1'35	1'35	0'00

TABLE II (contd.).

B. Fasciatus.			
<i>L</i> -Leucylglycylglycine ...	1'40 c.c.	4'10 c.c.	2'70 c.c.
<i>d</i> -Leucylglycylglycine ...	1'40	1'40	0'00
<i>Echis carinata</i> .			
<i>L</i> -Leucylglycylglycine ...	1'40 c.c.	5'66 c.c.	4'26 c.c.
<i>d</i> -Leucylglycylglycine ...	1'40	1'40	0'00

Carboxypolypeptidase.

Carboxypolypeptidase has been obtained in crystalline form by Anson (*Science*, 1935, **81**, 461). Bergmann, Zervas and Schleich (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1934, **224**, 45) have shown that it can hydrolyse peptides of the form XCONH·CRH·COOH, where X and R stand for univalent radicals. We searched for this enzyme in the venoms of *Naja naja*, *B. fasciatus*, *Echis carinata* and *Vipera russellii* using chloroacetyltyrosine as substrate. It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table III that the venoms mentioned above contain appreciable amount of carboxypolypeptidase. In the following experiments the concentration of the different venoms in the solutions was 0'1%, the concentration of the substrate was 0'008*M*, and the p_H of the solution 7'0 in each case.

TABLE III.

Substrate=Chloroacetyl-*l*-tyrosine.

0'01*N*-NaOH solution required (in c.c.) for the titration of 5 c.c. of the solution after 24 hours' incubation at 36°.

Type of venom used.	Control.	Venom + substrate.	Diff.
<i>Naja naja</i>	... 2'70	3'46	0'76
<i>Vipera russellii</i>	... 2'65	3'20	0'55
<i>B. fasciatus</i>	... 2'65	3'20	0'55
<i>Echis carinata</i>	... 2'70	5'25	2'55

Choline-esterase.

The existence of a choline-esterase was first suggested by Dale (*J. Pharm. Expt. Therap.*, 1914-15, 6, 141). It occurs in the blood and tissues such as heart muscle, intestinal mucosa, etc. of animals. It has been shown by Stedman and co-workers (*Biochem. J.*, 1932, 26, 2056; 1933, 27, 1055) and Plattner and co-workers (*Pfl. Arch.*, 1930, 228, 19) that it is specific in its action since it does not parallel the lipase content of various organs. Iyengar and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) have recently found that Cobra (*Naja naja*) venom possesses considerable cholin-esterase activity, whereas *Vipera russellii* shows practically no such activity. We have also found that *Naja naja* and *B. Fasciatus* venoms possess marked cholin-esterase activity, while the venoms of *Echis carinata*, *Vipera russellii* and *Crotalus-t-terrificus* show no such activity. This will be noticed from the data recorded in Table IV. Since acetylcholine is liberated from nerve-endings and mediates in the transmission of nerve impulse and since in cobra poisoning there occurs paralysis of the nervous system, Iyengar and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) put forward the hypothesis that the neurotoxin of cobra venom is probably identical with choline-esterase. They meant thereby that when a cobra neurotoxin is introduced into the animal system in sufficient amount, it causes immediate destruction of the acetylcholine liberated, and thus produces paralysis of the nervous system. We have, however, found that the purified cobra neurotoxin (M.L.D. 1/90 mg.) prepared by us does not possess choline-esterase activity. Furthermore, when solutions of crude cobra and *B. Fasciatus* venoms are heated at 60° or 70°, they completely lose their choline-esterase activity, while their neurotoxic activity remains practically unaltered. This will be evident from the data recorded in Table V. In these experiments the concentration of the substrate solutions was 0.625% in those cases where cobra venom was used; in the other cases it was 0.315%. The p_H of the solutions was adjusted to 7.0.

TABLE IV.

0.0143N-NaOH required (in c. c.) for the titration of 10 c. c. of the solution after 3 hours' incubation at 36°.

Type of venom.	Conc. of venom.	Control.	Venom + substrate.	Diff.
naja Naja	0.0125%	4.05	10.90 c.c.	6.25 c.c.
B. Fasciatus	0.0250	4.10	15.80	11.75
Vipera russellii	0.1250	4.10	4.10	0.00
Echis carinata	0.0125	4.10	4.10	0.00
Crotalus-t-terrificus	0.0125	4.10	4.10	0.00

TABLE V.

0.0143N-NaOH required (in c.c.) for the titration of 10 c.c. of the solution after 3 hours' incubation at 36°.

Type of venom.	Venom heated.	Conc. of venom.	Control	Venom+ substrate.	Diff.	Toxicity remain. ing.
Naja naja crude	60°	0.0125%	4.05 c.c.	4.05 c.c.	0.00 c.c.	>95%
	70°	0.0125	4.05	4.05	0.00	>90
Naja naja purified neurotoxin	36°	0.0125	4.05	4.05	0.00	100
B. Fasciatus	60°	0.025	4.05	4.10	0.05	>95
	70°	0.025	4.05	4.05	0.00	>80

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APPLIED CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

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